

From Visible to Invisible

Overseeing the archaeological remains at Pointe-à-Callière, the Montréal Archaeology and History Complex

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Pointe-à-Callière is a “site museum” built in 1992 over Montréal's birthplace. It preserves and displays archaeological remains and collections dating from the 13th to 19th centuries and bearing witness to the city's growth and Montrealers' lives.

The **Museum Complex** is composed of **7 separate pavilions and sites**:

- 1- The *Eperon* (Main building), housing Montréal's first Catholic cemetery (1643-1654) and the foundations of the once majestic Royal Insurance Company building (1861-1951)
- 2- The Old Customs House
- 3- The archaeological Crypt under the *Place Royale*
- 4- The Mariner's House
- 5- The Youville Pumping Station
- 6- The Warehouse preserving the archaeological remains of the Fort Ville-Marie (1642) and Callière's Château (1688)
- 7- The Stone Sewer Collector/ Little Saint-Pierre River (1838)

This presentation focuses on the conservation and monitoring of the archaeological remains located inside the main building, the *Eperon*.

ARCHAEOLOGY

Excavations were carried out in 1989 and 1990, immediately prior to the construction of Pointe-à-Callière Museum.

The **stratigraphy** of the site was quite simple :

- 1- Top stratum : the stone foundations of the Royal Insurance Company building (1861-1951)
- 2- middle stratum: the stone foundations of a warehouse (1811-1860)
- 3- bottom stratum: the natural ground and the burial ground (first cemetery of Montreal, 1643-1654)

All these vestiges are accessible to the public in the permanent exhibition, *Where Montreal was Born*.

CONSERVATION ISSUES IN THE EPERON BUILDING

- 1- The cemetery**
- 2- The Royal Insurance building (RIB) foundations**

1-The cemetery

The 17th century burial ground was a source of significant conservation challenges in the 1990s, due mainly to salt evaporation with resulting destruction of surface soils.

The challenge was met by installing a sealing membrane, a delicate operation involving the following steps:

- molding and removal of the overlying surface soil, section by section
- membrane installation
- putting the surface soil back in place .

The results of the operation were conclusive;. afterwards , deterioration stopped completely.

2- The Royal Insurance building (RIB) foundations

The remains of the RIB are composed of stone and brick walls and a stone slab floor. The whole basement level of the building has been preserved and now forms part of the permanent exhibit. Visitors can walk through the remains, stepping on the original floor.

Over the past 10 years, the site cumulated a series of structural problems, indicating that changes had occurred in the soils below the surface.

Nature of the problems

- broken coping stones
- cracking of some joints, mainly around the burial ground
- settling of the 19th century masonry

Starting in 1998, some of these problems became visually observable. The gaps were filled and the cracks sealed. Twice a year, cleaning and maintenance of the site was performed, and a logbook was filled with observed changes on the vestiges. But because we had no precise survey records to serve as reference tools, it was difficult to assess the extent of the settling. We kept track of the situation manually, noting and recording the dimensions of the cracks or damage and photographing them.

Understanding the sources of the problems

We had to survey the subsoils around the damaged area to understand the origin and causes of the problem.

The archaeological stratigraphy which had already been initially carried out, gave us some clues :

- the 19th century stone walls and floor rest on layers of clay
- wood planks and beams were also used as foundations beneath and behind the layers of clay

Methodoly used for identifying and locating the sources of the problems:

1. drilling test holes near critical areas
2. analyzing moisture/plasticity of clay and composition of understructures
3. 3D laser scans of the site on the long term to detect movements of structures

In 2009, an initial 3D laser digital survey was conducted of the entire site. Five permanent control points were set up. These georeferenced control points allowed us to link up the different scans and provided us with hitherto impossibly precise surveys of the entire site.

The following year, a second series of scans was conducted and by comparing the data we were able to visualize the changes that had occurred over the previous twelve months – in this case, settling of the stone slab floor and deformation of a soil retaining wall.

The data were displayed in the form of colours superimposed on the survey plan. Although these changes were imperceptible to the naked eye, the survey allowed us to identify at-risk areas and plan underpinning work as part of an overall preventive maintenance program for the site. These surveys have been conducted annually since then.

N°	Ref. X	Ref. Y	Ref. Z	Mes. X	Mes. Y	Mes. Z	Dev. X	Dev. Y	Dev. Z	Dev.
24	-12.587	12.491	-2.343	-12.592	12.488	-2.341	-0.004	-0.003	0.002	-0.006
25	-12.327	12.017	-2.376	-12.337	12.012	-2.372	-0.011	-0.005	0.004	-0.012
26	-11.984	11.434	-2.256	-11.999	11.428	-2.25	-0.015	-0.006	0.006	-0.017
27	-11.628	10.835	-2.147	-11.644	10.824	-2.146	-0.015	-0.011	0.001	-0.019
28	-11.763	13.139	-1.813	-11.762	13.138	-1.809	0	-0.001	0.004	-0.004
29	-11.403	12.705	-2.005	-11.402	12.705	-2.012	0.001	0	-0.006	0.006
30	-7.611	14.724	-1.928	-7.609	14.725	-1.949	0.002	0.001	-0.021	0.021

In 2010, a geotechnic survey with 2 drilling test holes was and 3 manual survey were performed by archaeologists and engineers in two areas, near the cemetery and in the multimedia room. The holes reached 2,43 m and 3,66 m deep.

Moisture and plasticity analysis of the clay presenting a normal natural water content and the plasticity grade was also good.

However, a wooden beam serving as a base for a foundation wall was located and found completely rotten, thus affecting the stability of the structure. It was identified as the probable main cause of the settling of the walls.

Restoration and stabilizing program of the site

The stabilization of the foundations, under engineer supervision, will be performed over the coming months.

The solutions include:

- Removing the rotten wood under the stone walls
- Replacing the wood by injecting a mixture of Urethane or, depending on the situation, a mixture of concrete.

Testing the different methods still need to be realized before using it more extensively under the fragile or damaged areas.

And since the factors of change on the site are continually evolving, the 3D scans and visual observations are the best methods to help us identify the areas where the underpinning works will need to be undertaken.